

Molecular Docking Study and Toxicity Profiling Support Neobavaisoflavone as a Potent and Safe Inhibitor of *Staphylococcus aureus* NorA Efflux Pump

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Abstract

Antibiotic resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus* is increasingly driven by efflux pumps such as NorA, which reduce the intracellular concentration of fluoroquinolones (such as ciprofloxacin). This has prompted the search for effective and safe efflux pump inhibitors (EPIs) as adjuvants to restore antibiotic efficacy. This study builds on prior *in vitro* findings that suggest promising bioactivity of neobavaisoflavone as a NorA efflux pump inhibitor, providing rationale for further investigation. Here, we employ *in silico* approaches to molecularly validate and elucidate its potential mechanisms of action. Using AutoDock Vina, the binding affinity and interactions of neobavaisoflavone were compared to an established reference inhibitor reserpine against the NorA crystal structure (PDB: 7L08). Neobavaisoflavone exhibited a strong binding affinity (-8.9 kcal/mol) and interacted with key binding site residues, particularly Arg310, Glu222, and Asp307, suggesting a competitive inhibition mechanism. *In silico* toxicity profiling with ProTox-3.0 predicted a more favorable safety profile for neobavaisoflavone compared to reserpine. The computational results align with and provide a mechanistic rationale for existing *in vitro* data, supporting neobavaisoflavone as a promising and safe efflux pump inhibitor candidate to combat antibiotic resistance in *S. aureus*. These findings support the development of plant-derived efflux pump inhibitors to combat antimicrobial resistance by enhancing intracellular retention of antibiotics. This positions neobavaisoflavone as a potential adjuvant or lead compound to restore fluoroquinolone efficacy in *S. aureus*.

Keywords: Molecular Docking, Neobavaisoflavone, NorA Efflux Pump, *Staphylococcus aureus*, Antibiotic Resistance, Efflux Pump Inhibitor

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Introduction

Over-expression of the NorA transporter in *Staphylococcus aureus* reduces intracellular concentrations of several fluoroquinolone antibiotics (e.g., ciprofloxacin, norfloxacin), which significantly contributes to antibiotic resistance and treatment failure. Therefore, researchers are expediting the search for alternative therapeutics or adjuvants that can improve bacterial susceptibility to conventional antibiotics (Gil-Gil et al., 2025; Palazzotti et al., 2023).

Natural products such as alkaloids are a rich source of efflux-pump inhibitors (EPIs) (Monteiro et al., 2020; Rodrigues et al., 2022). Particularly, prenylated isoflavonoids from Fabaceae have recently been identified as potent NorA inhibitors: Irianti et al., (2023) reported that several prenylated isoflavonoids (including neobavaisoflavone, glabrene and glyceollins) increased intracellular ethidium accumulation and reduced ciprofloxacin MICs in NorA-overexpressing *S. aureus*, demonstrating both efflux inhibition and, for some compounds, direct antimicrobial activity. Prenylated isoflavonoids are a subgroup of isoflavonoids that have a prenyl group attached to their chemical structure. The work of Irianti et al., (2023) allows researchers to test structure-activity of prenylated (iso)flavonoids as potential inhibitors of NorA.

NorA is a proton-coupled major facilitator superfamily (MFS) transporter whose substrate binding is architecturally large, consisting mainly of hydrophobic residues (Brawley et al., 2022; Bhaskar et al., 2016). Some residues such as Glu222, Asp307, Phe303 and Arg310 are implicated in substrate recognition and anchorage, making them important determinants

of inhibitor binding and transporter function (Brawley et al., 2022; Palazzotti et al., 2019; Zimmermann et al., 2019). Recent structural and supervised-MD studies provide atomic detail of substrate/inhibitor engagement and the proton-coupling mechanism, which can guide rational inhibitor design and interpretation of docking results.

Reserpine, a well-established reference inhibitor of NorA, known to have antihypertensive properties (Weir, 2020; Zhu et al., 2019), is not used clinically as a result of documented *in vivo* toxicity including neurotoxicity (Govindarajulu, et al., 2021; Salimikia & Heidari, 2023; Strawbridge et al., 2023). Even though it is not a clinically approved drug, it is being used widely as a benchmark for *in silico* and *in vitro* studies involving NorA and VMAT (vesicular monoamine transporters) (Zimmermann et al., 2019; Metzger, et al., 2002; Nall & Sehgal, 2013). Molecular docking and other in-silico approaches are invaluable for screening and prioritizing phytochemical scaffolds such as prenylated isoflavonoids. However, docking predictions alone do not prove biological activity.

Despite the promising experimental findings of Irianti et al., (2023), which demonstrated that neobavaisoflavone exhibits comparable or superior NorA efflux pump inhibitory activity relative to reserpine, alongside a more favorable safety profile, these observations remain largely empirical and lack detailed molecular-level validation. Hence, a critical gap persists in elucidating the structural and mechanistic basis for these effects. Therefore, this study addresses this gap by employing *in silico* techniques to provide molecular validation of neobavaisoflavone's interaction with NorA efflux

pump, as well as its therapeutic safety. The results of this study will be integrated with experimentally (*in vitro*)-derived results (MIC shifts, ethidium accumulation, efflux assays, cytotoxicity testing) to evaluate the efficacy and safety of neobavaisoflavone as an EPI candidate.

Materials and Methods

Ligand Retrieval and Preparation

Reserpine was selected as benchmark because of its well-established NorA inhibitory activity (Irianti et al., 2023; Zimmermann et al., 2019; Markham et al., 1999; Schmitz et al., 1998; Aeschlimann et al., 1999).

The three-dimensional (3D) structure of reserpine and neobavaisoflavone were retrieved from PubChem database. Reserpine (CID: 5770)

and Neobavaisoflavone (CID: 57481834) (**Table 1**) were downloaded in SDF (structure data file) format and imported into Avogadro (v. 1.2.0), where hydrogens were added at physiological (blood) pH (7.4) and energy-minimized via MMFF94 force field on Avogadro (v. 1.2.0) to relieve them of any geometrical constraint. After energy minimization, the ligands were exported and saved in PDB (protein data bank) format. The ligands were imported into ADT (AutoDockTools) (v. 1.5.7) for the assignment of Gasteiger partial charges and definition of rotatable bonds. After this, the ligands were exported and saved in PDBQT format in preparation for docking. The PDBQT format is an extension of the standard PDB that incorporates partial atomic charges (Q), AutoDock atom types (T), and torsional degrees of freedom, needed by AutoDock Vina for the evaluation of electrostatic interactions and flexibility of the ligands during docking.

Table 1. Molecular Weight and 2D Structures of the Reserpine and Neobavaisoflavone

Compound	Chemical Formula	MW (g/mol)	HA/HD	RB	2D Structure
Reserpine	C ₃₃ H ₄₀ N ₂ O ₉	608.7	10/1	10	
Neobavaisoflavone	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₄	328.4	4/2	3	

MW=molecular weight; *HA*=hydrogen bond acceptor; *HD*=hydrogen bond donor; *RB*=rotatable bond

Protein Retrieval and Preparation

Brawley et al., (2022) released the first experimentally determined 3D structures of NorA

efflux pump from *S. aureus* in 2022. Two cryo-EM NorA structures bound to Fab fragments (PDB 7LO8 and 7LO7) were released, finally providing high-resolution templates for structure-based

research including drug design and development (Palazzotti et al., 2023). The NorA efflux pump protein of *Staphylococcus aureus* (PDB ID: 7LO8; cryo-EM, 3.16 Å) (**Figure 1**) was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank. This structure has been previously validated and employed in NorA inhibitor studies, including (Palazzotti et al., 2023), further supporting its suitability and reliability for structure-based analyses. The

Figure 1. Cryo-EM outward-facing (C_{out}) structure of *S. aureus* NorA efflux pump (PDB: 7LO8) used for docking studies, without the Fab fragments (removed during protein preparation).

Grid Generation, Docking Validation, and Data Analysis

NorA was co-crystallized with protein inhibitor Fab fragments (comprising heavy chain H:262 and light chain L:238 residues). Hence, it is not feasible to validate the docking results using conventional methods such as re-docking, which require co-crystallized non-peptide small molecule. Therefore, the cartesian coordinates of the orthosteric (primary) pocket of NorA applied in docking the ligands were automatically predicted as $x = 138.033$, $y = 136.349$, and $z = 156.979$ by ADT based on the protein's large central cavity. Bhaskar et al. (2016), noted that NorA consists of a conspicuously large, hydrophobic pocket. Using the *Define and Edit Binding Site* function on BIOVIA Discovery Studio, the previously generated binding site on ADT was corroborated ($x = 138.032726$, $y = 136.348918$, $z = 156.979108$). A grid dimension of $40 \times 40 \times 40$ Å was used to dock the ligands. However, docking accuracy was assessed based on interactions with key residues identified via

structure was pre-processed in BIOVIA Discovery Studio 2025 (Dassault Systèmes) by removing water molecules and other heteroatoms. After this, the protein was exported and processed in AutoDockTools, where polar hydrogens were introduced, Gasteiger charges were added, and the final structure was converted to PDBQT format for docking.

experimental techniques, molecular docking, and supervised molecular dynamics (SuMD).

Molecular Docking

Molecular docking was performed by AutoDock Vina (The Scripps Research Institute, La Jolla, USA) (Trott & Olson, 2010) to predict the binding orientation and affinity of the reference and test ligands toward the proteins. AutoDock Vina is an open-source docking program that employs an iterative global search algorithm and an empirical scoring function to estimate binding free energies based on intermolecular interactions such as hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic contacts, attractive charge, π -interactions, van der Waals forces.

Docking was executed via the command-line interface (cmd.exe). The working directory contained the prepared receptor (.pdbqt), ligand (.pdbqt), and configuration (.txt) files. AutoDock Vina was invoked by specifying the executable path and defining the respective input and output files (log.txt and output.pdbqt).

Toxicity Profiling

Toxicity assessment of reserpine and neobavaisoflavone was performed using Protox – 3.0 (<https://tox.charite.de/protox3>) (Banerjee et al., 2024), which focuses on oral acute toxicity (LD₅₀) prediction. Four key toxicity endpoints were evaluated: hepatotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, neurotoxicity, and cytotoxicity. Neurotoxicity specifically included due to the clinically documented adverse effects of reserpine. Cytotoxicity was further considered based in the *in vitro* study by (Irianti et al., 2023), which reported that, despite exhibiting similar NorA efflux pump inhibitory potential, neobavaisoflavone demonstrated lower cytotoxicity compared to reserpine. This integrated approach allowed a comparative assessment of safety profiles *in silico*, complementing the experimental observations.

Results

The docking poses for reserpine and neobavaisoflavone were evaluated for biological

relevance based on their interaction with residues identified as binding site-specific residues, as defined by Palazzotti et al. (2023), to perform supervised molecular dynamics (SuMD). SuMD tracks the trajectory of compounds during simulations. Prior to SuMD simulations, the inhibitory site was characterized by Palazzotti et al., (2023) through an analysis of Fab36-NorA complex. Their work outlined that the binding site comprised of Asn137, Phe140, Phe303, Asp307, Arg310, Glu222, and Thr223, emphasizing the crucial role of Glu222 and Asp307 in substrate recognition and anchorage. Carboxylate groups on Glu222 and Asp307 create a key anionic, electron-rich pocket involved in proton cycling (Palazzotti et al., 2023; Brawley et al., 2022; Palazzotti et al., 2019). Hence, ligand association with these residues potentially interferes with proton translocation steps and suppresses NorA-mediated efflux of antibiotics. This study was justified based on interaction with the site-specific residues as characterized by Palazzotti et al. (2023) (**Table 2**).

Table 2. Comparison of Binding Site Residues and Compound Interactions in NorA

Residue	Interaction with Reserpine?	Interaction with Neobavaisoflavone?
Asn137	Yes (non-classical hydrogen bond)	Yes (non-classical hydrogen bond)
Phe140	Yes (electrostatic force)	Yes (hydrophobic force)
Glu222	Yes (electrostatic force)	Yes (electrostatic force, non-classical hydrogen bond)
Thr223	Yes (dispersion force)	No
Asp307	Yes (non-classical hydrogen bond)	Yes (electrostatic force)
Phe303	Yes (dispersion force)	Yes (hydrophobic force)
Arg310	Yes (classical hydrogen bond)	Yes (classical hydrogen bond)

Results of SuMD simulations showed that ciprofloxacin established the most contacts with the following residues: Ile23, Phe140, Glu222, Tyr225, Ile244, Phe140, Phe303, and Arg310

(Palazzotti et al., 2019). Therefore, the credibility of the docking was also assessed based on significant interaction with these hotspot residues (**Table 3**).

Table 3. Summary of Binding Affinity and Interaction Profile

Compound	Binding Affinity (kcal/mol)	Interacting Hotspot Residues (Ile23, Phe140, Glu222, Tyr225, Ile244, Phe303, and Arg310)	Total No. of Interacting Hotspot Residues (7)
Reserpine (control)	-9.4	F140, E222, I244, F303, and *R310.	5
Neobavaisoflavone	-8.9	F140, E222, Y225, *I244, F303, and *R310.	6

*conventional hydrogen bond

Two-dimensional (2D) interaction diagrams (**Figure 2**) were generated by BIOVIA Discovery Studio to visualize the specific amino acids residues involved in the ligand binding within the orthosteric (primary) pocket of NorA. Both reserpine and neobavaisoflavone formed classical hydrogen bond with Arg310.

a

b

Figure 2. Molecular Interactions Stabilizing the Protein-Ligand Complex. (a)Reserpine; (b)Neobavaiosflavone.

To highlight the spatial occupancy and orientation of the ligands in the primary pocket of NorA, three-dimensional images (**Figure 3**) of the

protein-ligand complex were generated on BIOVIA Discovery Studio.

Figure 3. 3D ribbon representation of the NorA efflux pump showing the ligands bound at the primary substrate-binding site. The protein is displayed in ribbon format and the ligands are shown in ball and stick representation within the large, hydrophobic pocket of the protein. (a) Reserpine; (b) Neobavaisoflavone.

ProTox-3.0 was used to predict toxicity, LD₅₀ (mg/kg), and assign compounds to toxicity classes 1 – 6. The predicted toxicity and LD₅₀ (median lethal dose) values, which is indicative of

the toxicity class, are presented in **Table 4**. The table also contains other toxicity endpoints: hepatotoxicity, neurotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, and cytotoxicity.

Table 4. *In silico* Toxicity Predictions for Reserpine and Neobavaisoflavone

Compound	LD ₅₀ (mg/kg)	Toxicity Class	Hepa	Neuro	Nephro	Cyto
Reserpine	300	3	Inactive	inactive	Active	Active
Neobavaisoflavone	2500	5	Inactive	inactive	Active	Inactive

Toxicity Class Key: 1 (most lethal) to 6 (non-toxic); active=predicted toxic effect, inactive=little or no predicted toxic effect. Hepa=hepatotoxicity; Neuro=neurotoxicity; Nephro=nephrotoxicity; Cyto=cytotoxicity.

Discussion

Efflux pump inhibition has emerged as a very important strategy to combat multi-drug resistance especially in MRSA, which have shown strong resistance to fluoroquinolones including ciprofloxacin and norfloxacin, via NorA-mediated efflux (Hamad et al., 2024). Molecular docking is

an *in silico* technique used to predict the binding affinity between a potential drug, known as ligand, and a protein target or any other macromolecule. However, prediction does not equate biological activity; hence, results of *in silico* studies must be validated experimentally (Pantsar & Poso, 2018; Meng et al., 2011)

Reserpine exhibited slightly stronger binding affinity compared to neobavaisoflavone (-9.4 vs. -8.9 kcal/mol). The docking score (-9.4 kcal/mol) obtained for reserpine is identical to that reported by Zimmermann et al. (2019) demonstrating strong agreement and supporting the reliability of our docking protocol. While Zimmermann et al., 2019 employed a homology-modelled NorA protein for docking, this study utilized the experimentally determined NorA structure. Despite the differences in the method of protein elucidation, both studies implemented AutoDock Vina and achieved comparable docking scores, supporting the reliability and reproducibility of the computational approach. In addition to the consistency in docking score, reserpine and neobavaisoflavone interacted with 100% and 86%, respectively, with the binding site residues identified and characterized by Palazzotti et al. (2019). Also, the ability of reserpine and neobavaisoflavone to efficiently interact with Arg310 (via classical hydrogen bond) strongly support our docking protocol and strong their inhibitory activity against NorA (Santos et al., 2023; Jerusha et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2025). The compounds interacted with negatively charged Glu222 and Asp307; this is an important criterion for a strong inhibitor. Ciprofloxacin, which is positively charged at physiological pH, can be electrostatically attracted to acidic residues such as Glu222 and Asp307 of NorA, thereby stabilizing its initial binding before efflux. Indicative of competitive inhibition, neobavaisoflavone formed electrostatic interactions with Glu222 and Asp307, and additionally established a non-classical hydrogen bond with Glu222, thereby further stabilizing the ligand-protein complex. Similarly, reserpine established strong electrostatic interaction with Glu222 and a non-classical hydrogen bond with Asp307.

Previous experimental work by Irianti et al. (2023) demonstrated that neobavaisoflavone robustly inhibits NorA and restores antibiotic susceptibility. In our study, we performed *in silico* validation to evaluate the findings of Irianti et al. (2023), who reported that neobavaisoflavone exhibited similar inhibitory potential to the classical reference inhibitor, reserpine. In

addition to the strong inhibitory potential of neobavaisoflavone, Irianti et al., 2023 also reported that neobavaisoflavone exhibited lower cytotoxicity compared to reserpine.

Irianti et al. (2023), reported that neobavaisoflavone significantly enhances intracellular ethidium accumulation in NorA overexpressing *S. aureus* SA-1199B by approximately 4.5±0.4-fold, whereas reserpine produced only ~2-fold increase. Moreover, neobavaisoflavone reduced ciprofloxacin MIC by 4-fold at ~3.125µg/mL (~10µM) and up to 8-fold at ~6.25 µg/mL (~19µM), outperforming reserpine tested at 6.25 µg/mL (~19µM), which achieved only 4-fold reduction. These experimental observations underscore neobavaisoflavone's superior functional inhibition of NorA even at comparable or lower concentrations.

Our molecular docking analysis supported these experimental findings. Even though reserpine exhibited marginally stronger binding affinity, both reserpine and neobavaisoflavone interacted with the key residues in the primary binding pocket of NorA. In addition, they formed stable interactions with these key residues, which further stabilized the interactions. While reserpine interacted with 71% (5 out of 7) of the residues observed, via SuMD (Palazzotti et al., 2019) to make the most interactions with ciprofloxacin, neobavaisoflavone interacted with 86% (6 out of 7) of these residues. Their interaction profiles show that they share the same binding site with ciprofloxacin, which is indicative of competitive inhibition (Chandal et al., 2023; Shaheen et al., 2019). The similarity in key residues engagement suggests that neobavaisoflavone occupies a physiologically relevant binding pose and operated through a mechanism analogous to reserpine. The fact that neobavaisoflavone demonstrated a superior functional inhibition *in vitro* despite a slightly weaker binding score implies that binding energetics alone do not determine efflux inhibition performance. Hence, additional molecular or membrane-associated dynamics likely favor neobavaisoflavone in a biological context.

In silico toxicity prediction using Protox-3.0 further distinguished the two compounds. According (Banerjee et al., 2024), ProTox 3.0 classifies compounds into six acute-oral toxicity categories based on predicted LD₅₀ values (mg/kg). Protox-3.0 classified neobavaisoflavone as acute oral toxicity class 5 (2500mg/kg), whereas reserpine fell into class 3 (300mg/g). The LD₅₀ of the compounds indicates that neobavaisoflavone has a higher safety margin than reserpine. These toxicity results is in agreement with experimentally-derived results by (Irianti et al., 2023), which reported that, based on cell viability experiments, neobavaisoflavone exhibited minimal cytotoxicity up to ~39 μ M, whereas reserpine exhibited measurable cytotoxicity at similar or even lower concentrations. The results of cytotoxicity end points by Protox-3.0, where neobavaisoflavone was predicted as inactive and reserpine is predicted as active, further strengthens the favorable toxicity profile of neobavaisoflavone. Reserpine and neobavaisoflavone were predicted to be inactive for neurotoxicity. However, clinically validated reports indicate that reserpine exerts neurotoxic effects including depression (Govindarajulu, et al., 2021; Salimikia & Heidari, 2023; Strawbridge et al., 2023). This is a major reason it is not used clinically even though it has antihypertensive properties. This finding underscores the need to interpret *in silico* predictions with caution; hence, it is important to experimentally and clinically validate findings to ensure reliability with regards to safety and efficacy (Raies & Bajic, 2016).

Interestingly, the results of the experimental study by Irianti et al., (2023), also highlighted that neobavaisoflavone may have intrinsic antibacterial activity, with MIC and MBC values of 12.5 μ g/mL and 25 μ g/mL, respectively. While docking alone cannot confirm additional antimicrobial mechanisms, the predicted favorable binding profile and efflux inhibition support a primary NorA-mediated mode of action. Therefore, further mechanistic interrogation through molecular dynamics, multi-target docking, or experimental assays is needed to fully understand the additional antimicrobial activities of neobavaisoflavone.

Conclusion

Altogether, our in-silico findings support and mechanistically rationalize the in-vitro findings, which demonstrates strong NorA inhibition, favorable toxicity predictions, and a mechanistic basis for the superior biological activity of neobavaisoflavone compared to reserpine. These findings reinforces neobavaisoflavone as a promising NorA efflux pump inhibitor or scaffold and a potential safe adjuvant for restoring fluoroquinolone efficacy in resistant *S. aureus*.

Limitation of Study

Even though molecular docking study provide valuable mechanistic insight into the protein-ligand interaction, a key limitation of this study is the absence of molecular dynamics simulation which provides further insight into the stability and temporal behavior of the protein-ligand complex.

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